

GENERAL CHARACTERISTICS OF DRAINAGE WATERS IN THE GRANTCHARITSA TUNGSTEN DEPOSIT, BULGARIA

Eugenia Tarassova¹, Aleksey Benderev², Elena Tacheva¹, Milen Stavrev², Valentina Lyubomirova³, and Mihail Tarassov¹

¹Institute of Mineralogy and Crystallography, Bulgarian Academy of Sciences, Acad. G. Bonchev Street 107, 1113 Sofia, Bulgaria. E-mail: mptarassov@gmail.com

²Geological Institute, Bulgarian Academy of Sciences, Acad. G. Bonchev Street 24, 1113 Sofia Bulgaria

³Faculty of Chemistry and Pharmacy, Sofia University, James Bourchier Blvd. 1, 1164 Sofia, Bulgaria

ABSTRACT: *The article describes the main types of drainage waters within the Grantcharitsa tungsten deposit: acid mine drainage, neutral to slightly acidic mine drainage, waters draining the oxidation zone of the deposit and underground waters of the meadow soils located above the oxidation zone. It is shown that the acid mine drainage accompanied by the precipitation of iron oxides (ferrihydrite) and the drainage waters of the oxidation zone and meadow soils have the most critical impact on the environment in the area of the deposit.*

Key words: *drainage waters, oxidation zone, tungsten deposit*

INTRODUCTION

Drainage waters in ore deposits before, during and after their exploitation are of particular importance for environmental protection, which is why a significant number of research articles and reviews have been published on this problem, and especially on acid mine drainage, which often contains elevated levels of dissolved metals, non-metals and metalloids, which are recognized as a potential environmental concern (Nordstrom et al. 2015; Akcil & Koldas 2006). The Grantcharitsa tungsten deposit (Bulgaria) has not been exploited yet, although it is one of the largest and promising tungsten objects in Europe. The deposit is located in the Western Rhodopes, on the territory of the Velingrad municipality, Pazardzhik region. It is named after the Grantcharitsa river and is situated southwest, 18 km in a straight line, from the town of Velingrad – a modern resort town and SPA center of Bulgaria. Ore mineralization in the deposit occurs in pegmatoid quartz-feldspar veins and in the surrounding rocks in the form of vein-disseminated ores ("mineralized granitoids"). The mineral composition of the vein ores is characterized by a sharp predominance of quartz and potassium feldspar (microcline) among the gangue minerals, as well as pyrite and scheelite among the ore minerals. The detailed exploration of the deposit was carried out in the period 1960-1990. During this period, more than 24.4 thousand meters of mine workings and more than 164.4 thousand meters of wells were made in the region and reserves of tungsten ore were proven (Mirchev 1995), however, industrial mining of tungsten was not carried out. Since 2009 the preparation for exploitation of the deposit has started, but in 2017 all activities in the Grantcharitsa deposit have been suspended due to the negative opinion of green activists and part of the local population and due to the establishment post factum in 2017 of the Sanitary Protection Zones on the Grantcharitsa river and its tributaries with borders that pass through the richest ores of the deposit. The main problem opponents of mining in the deposit see in the risk of water pollution and is related to the fact that in the western part of the deposit, on the Grantcharitsa river, there are facilities for water intake into the Bistritsa derivation conduit, built in the 1950s as one of several to feed the Batak dam lake and the Batak hydroelectric power station. The Bistritsa conduit is partially used for technical and domestic needs of the town of Velingrad.

In the period 2019-2023, the authors conducted a series of studies of the geochemical behavior of tungsten within the deposit, including the oxidation zone, soils, sediments and waters. The present study gives general information on the hydrochemistry of the drainage waters within the deposit. Detailed water research data will be published in upcoming articles. The emphasis here is placed on waters with a possible potential negative effect on the environment, namely the waters flowing from exploratory mining workings (prospecting galleries) and their waste dumps, and the waters draining the oxidation zone of the deposit and in direct contact with the groundwater in the flood terraces of the Grantcharitsa river. The earlier studies of the waters, cited in Mirchev (1995), show that both surface and underground waters are dilute, pH 6-8, mostly hydrogen carbonate-sulfate, calcium-magnesium. The total mineralization increases from surface-flowing waters (Grantcharitsa river and tributaries) (50-80 mg/L) to fracture ground and fracture vein waters - up to 150 mg/L.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

Water sampling points were selected taking into account a potential negative environmental effect on the surface flowing waters of the Grantcharitsa river and its tributaries (Fig. 1): (1) western part of the deposit - waters flowing from abandoned and buried galleries and their heaps (sampling location A); (2) central part of the deposit - underground waters of the flood terrace of the Grantcharitsa river, located on the oxidation zone of the deposit, and rare seepage waters draining the oxidation zone (sampling location B); (3) eastern part of the deposit - waters in prospecting galleries with weakly pronounced oxidation processes (sampling location C). Water samples for dissolved cations and trace metals were filtered in the field conditions using a syringe (50 ml) and 0.45 μm membrane filter into polyethylene bottle (100 ml) and then acidified by Suprapur 65% HNO_3 (Sigma-Aldrich) to $\text{pH} \sim 1$. Unfiltered water samples were collected in 1 l polyethylene bottles for anion analyses. Additionally, in order to establish the role of suspended substances in waters, as well as in the colloidal state, analyses of the dry residue of the selected water samples were conducted. To evaluate the role of suspended substances in waters with high content of iron ($>0.2 \text{ mg/L}$), the water sample without filtration was placed in a polyethylene bottle (100 ml) and then acidified by Suprapur 65% HNO_3 (Sigma-Aldrich) to $\text{pH} \sim 1$.

Field measurements of pH, temperature, electric conductivity, dissolved oxygen (DO) and redox potential (ORP) of waters were carried out using portable multiparameter instrument. Laboratory examinations included analysis of water samples by ICP-OES and ICP-MS and dry residuals and drainage sediments – by SEM-EDS, LA-ICP-MS and XRD.

Figure 1. Water sampling location in the area of the Grantcharitsa deposit (modified geological map of Sarov et al. (2010) with ore zones according to Mirchev (1995)): location A - waters flowing from abandoned and buried galleries (acid drainage); location B - underground waters of the flood terrace of the Grantcharitsa river above the oxidation zone and seepage waters draining the oxidation zone; location C - waters from abandoned prospecting gallery (neutral to slightly acidic drainage)

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

First we will start with the characteristics that are common to all types of water. (i) Our research shows that all the investigated waters (groundwater and drainage waters from abandoned prospecting galleries – waters affected by mining activity) are diluted, with a total electrical conductivity varying between 70 and 170 $\mu\text{S/cm}$, which is a confirmation of the data 30 years ago (Mirchev, 1995). (ii) With few exceptions (acid mine drainage), the predominant part of the waters is characterized by a hydrogen

carbonate-sulfate-silicate anion composition and a predominantly calcium-sodium cation composition and pH 5.8-7.2. The specific features of individual types of drainage water are discussed below.

Acid mine drainage from abandoned prospecting galleries

This type of drainage waters is more typical for the western part of the deposit (Fig. 1, location A). When these waters are discharged from a closed adit, abundant deposition of iron oxide precipitates (mainly ferrihydrite) is observed (Tarassov et al. 2020). Preliminary hydrochemistry data of the waters given in (Tarassov et al. 2023) show that the waters are characterized with pH 4.4-6.0 and EC 100-140 $\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$ and have sulfate-silicate anionic and calcium-sodium cationic composition and contain also Fe 0.2-3.3 mg/L and W 0.19-3.5 $\mu\text{g}/\text{L}$. It has been found that the pH of the waters depends on the climatic conditions – the pH falls when the season is wet (corresponds to high water) and rises when the season is dry (low water). The lowest value of pH = 2.6 of the waters was measured by us in April 2019 during an intense snow melt, but since this measurement we have not recorded a pH of the waters less than 4.4. The high variations in the pH of acid mine drainage is typical for territories with seasonally wet-dry climate such as northern Australia where ephemeral acid mine drainage exist during rainy season (Harris et al. 2003). It is possible that the same model operates in acid drainage of the Grantcharitsa deposit. The acid drainage in the western part of the deposit has the most significant impact on the environment of the area, as these waters directly flow into the Bistritsa derivation conduit. Precipitation of iron oxides can be seen as self-purification of waters - iron oxides have been found to almost completely absorb tungsten from water at a distance of up to 3 meters. But the problem arises during intense rainfall or snowmelt, when the deposited iron oxide sediments are carried as a suspension in the river system of the deposit. It should be noted that we did not detect any negative impact of waste dumps remaining after exploration adits on the quality of surface waters.

Neutral to slightly acidic mine drainage

We found drainage of this type in the eastern part of the deposit (Fig. 1, location C). This drain is characterized by an almost stagnant character of the gallery floor waters with very little discharge at the gallery entrance. Oxidation processes on the ores are weakly manifested. There is no precipitation of secondary iron oxide minerals. The measured values of pH are 6.7-7.0 and EC are 80-130 $\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$. These waters are characterized by very low Fe contents – 0.01 mg/L and the highest W contents for the mine drainage of the deposit – 15-16 $\mu\text{g}/\text{L}$. The effect of this drainage on the environment is minimal. In our opinion, within the Grantcharitsa deposit, the development of acid or neutral mine drainage in the mine workings is related not only to the hydrochemical characteristics of the specific terrain or gallery, but also to the presence of oxidized ores even before the gallery is passed. The oxidation zone of the deposit is more developed in the central and western part of the deposit.

Drainage of the oxidation zone and flood terrace of the Grantcharitsa river

A common feature of soils in areas with current and past mining and metallurgical activities is the tendency for W content to increase in the surface soil layer, caused by surface and airborne transport (Zheng et al. 2020). An increase of W content in topsoil to ~100 ppm was found by us for the meadow soil located above the oxidation zone of the Grantcharitsa deposit (Tarassov et al. 2023) (Fig. 1, location B). The reason for this is not surface or airborne transport of tungsten mineral particles, but direct connection of the groundwater with the waters draining the oxidation zone. Sequential extraction showed that 65% of the W in the topsoil was associated with soil organic matter and ferrihydrite. Although the connection between the groundwater and the waters draining the oxidation zone and is proven by indirect methods, in some cases the latter waters come to the surface of the soil as seepage with intensive precipitation of iron oxides (ferrihydrite). The occurrence of seepage is not often phenomenon and is directly connected with the water saturation of the oxidation zone and climatic conditions. The studied by us seepage from April 2022 is characterized by pH = 6.2, EC = 110 $\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$ and a hydrogen carbonate-silicate-sulfate anionic and calcium-sodium cationic composition. The content of Fe and W is 2.2 mg/L and 1.2 $\mu\text{g}/\text{L}$, respectively.

The groundwater associated with waters draining the oxidation zone are characterized by pH 5.8-7.2, EC 66-80 $\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$ and a hydrogen carbonate-sulfate-silicate anionic and calcium-sodium cationic composition. The essential part of such elements as Fe and W in the composition of groundwater is not ions or molecules, but are present as particulate matter. The maximal content of Fe and W found by us in the groundwater is 5.2 mg/L and 28 $\mu\text{g}/\text{L}$, respectively, from which only 0.94 mg/L (Fe) and 2.9 $\mu\text{g}/\text{L}$ (W) can be related to ionic and molecular form (according to ICP-MS analysis of filtered and acidified by HNO_3 sample). The established connection between the groundwater and the waters draining the oxidation

zone is not directly related to the quality of the surface waters entering the Bistritsa derivation, but it has an important ecological significance in another aspect, namely: these waters can lead to the inclusion of tungsten in the nutrient chain. This is related to the fact that the floodplain meadows near the Grantcharitsa river have long been used by the local people to prepare hay for raising animals.

In addition to the mentioned drainage waters, springs with free-flowing water, which has no relation to the ores of the deposit and is used for drinking purposes, have been established within the deposit.

CONCLUSIONS

1. The all studied waters are diluted, with a total electrical conductivity varying between 70 and 170 $\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$. With the exception of acid mine drainage, the majority of waters are characterized by hydrogen carbonate-sulfate-silicate anionic and calcium-sodium cation composition and pH 5.8-7.2.

2. Two types of mine drainage have been identified in the Grantcharitsa deposit: acid mine drainage and neutral to slightly acidic mine drainage. Acid mine drainage has a critical impact on the environment in the deposit area.

3. The established connection between the groundwater and the waters draining the oxidation zone have important environmental impacts - they can lead to the inclusion of tungsten in the food chain.

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